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АННОТАЦИЯ

В сегодняшнем все более современном обществе человечество сталкивается со многими проблемами, которые необходимо решать. Это, в свою очередь, приводит ко многим стрессовым ситуациям в повседневной жизни. Психосоциальные факторы присутствуют в жизни людей всех возрастов и могут приводить к развитию неинфекционных заболеваний. Ишемическая болезнь сердца, особенно стенокардия, инфаркт миокарда (ИМ) уже давно стали обычным явлением в современном обществе. Неблагоприятная экологическая обстановка и загрязнение атмосферы вредными отходами производства приводят к росту сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний у малоподвижного населения.

Ключевые слова: инфаркт миокарда, ишемическая болезнь сердца, ожирение.

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Samarkand, Uzbekistan**Turaev Hikmatilla Negmatovich**Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan**ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AS A SOCIALLY SIGNIFICANT PROBLEM****ANNOTATION**

In today's increasingly modern society, humanity faces many challenges that need to be addressed. This, in turn, leads to many stressful situations in everyday life. Psychosocial factors are present in the lives of people of all ages and can lead to the development of noncommunicable diseases. Ischemic heart disease, especially angina pectoris, myocardial infarction (MI) has long been a common occurrence in modern society. The unfavorable ecological situation and air pollution with harmful production wastes lead to an increase in cardiovascular diseases in the sedentary population.

Keywords: myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, obesity.

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MIOKARD INFARKTI DOLZARB IJTIMOY AHAMIYATGA EGA BO'LGAN MUAMMO SIFATIDA

ANNOTATSIYA

Bugungi kunda tobora rivojlanib borayotgan zamonaviy jamiyatda insoniyat yuqori ko'plab hal qilinishi zarur bo'lgan muammolarga duch kelmoqda. Bu esa o'z navbatida kundalik hayotda ko'plab stressli holatlarni keltirib chiqaradi. Psixosotsial omil har qanday yoshdagi odamlarning hayotida mavjud va ular yuqumli bo'lmagan kasalliklarning rivojlanishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Koronar qon tomir kasalliklari, xususan, stenokardiyalar, miokard infarkti (MI) uzoq vaqtdan beri zamonaviy jamiyatda qayd tez-tez qayd etilmoqda. Noqulay ekologik sharoit va atmosferaning zararli sanoat chiqindilari bilan ifloslanib borishi kam harakatlilik insonlar populyatsiyasida yurak qon tomir kasalliklari ortishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: miokard infarkti, yurak ishemik kasalligi, qandli diabet, semizlik.

Nowadays, coronary heart disease is one of the main causes of death in the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with pathology of cerebral vessels and oncological diseases. In 2017, 59.9 per cent of registered deaths (96,738 cases) were due to diseases of the circulatory system. According to the data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, among people 45-65 years old, 2/3 of deaths from cardiovascular diseases are related to cardiovascular diseases, especially myocardial infarction [4, 11, 8].

Coronary heart disease is one of the main causes of death in many developed countries. For example, in Russia, myocardial infarction is diagnosed annually in 0.2-0.6% of men aged 40-59 years and in 1.7% of men aged 60-64 years. In middle-aged women, acute myocardial infarction develops 2.5-5 times less frequently than in men; the difference in morbidity between men and women aged 60 years and older is significantly reduced [3].

There are few initial chances of impacting on improving the epidemiological status of primary cardiac arrest, as only 2-5% of cases are able to apply successful resuscitative measures. Furthermore, the chances of success in resuscitative measures are decreasing by the minute. Considering that in 80% of cases death occurs at home, in 15% of cases death occurs on the street or in a public place. About 2500 people die suddenly every day in the European Union countries and this number of sudden coronary deaths (primary cardiac arrest) worldwide is about 3000000 per year [6].

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Myocardial infarction caused by coronary insufficiency is one of the serious diseases characterised by high mortality. 50 years ago, the treatment methods for myocardial infarction were not definitive. Mortality from acute myocardial infarction was about 30% or more [15, 16].

According to evidence-based medicine, the introduction of modern treatment methods in the first place significantly reduces mortality from this disease. Currently, in modern European clinics, the mortality rate in this illness reaches 5% [27].

Statistics show that primary and total morbidity are 2069.2 (60% increase) and 6062.0 (30% increase) respectively. This increase will be mainly due to the increase in the studied indicators among adults, so that the primary morbidity among people over 18 years of age will increase by 1.1 from 1960.6 in 2003 to 2230.0 in 2020; the total will increase by 1.86 times from 7305.8 to 13591.2 respectively. This discrepancy

between the growth rates of primary and total morbidity among the adult population will be due not only to the chronology of the process, but also to the increasing proportion of elderly people in the population, as the country is experiencing a trend towards a decreasing birth rate and increasing life expectancy. If the conditions for which the 2020 projections for children and adolescents are calculated are maintained, primary morbidity will decrease by a factor of 1.2 and 1.6, respectively; total morbidity decreases by a factor of 2.1 and 1.5, respectively.

Dynamics of myocardial infarction incidence in the United States: about 5 million patients with chest pain are admitted to the emergency department each year, of whom about 1 million are diagnosed with MI. [1, 2]. The European Society of Cardiology guidelines for the management of patients with MI state that one in six men and one in seven women in Europe die from MI. [6]. The same document notes that the incidence of myocardial infarction and hospitalisation with it varies significantly between countries. In Sweden, AMI is diagnosed in an average of 66 out of 100,000 inhabitants per year. Similar data were observed in the Czech Republic and Belgium. [8].

Epidemiological studies have repeatedly confirmed the role of risk factors in the development of coronary heart disease, in particular myocardial infarction. Although risk factors for coronary heart disease are generally well known, the importance of each of them varies in different regions and among different population groups [9]. It is known that coronary heart disease has a different course and lasts longer than always in most cases myocardial infarction can occur [12]. In some patients with coronary heart disease, myocardial infarction does not occur at all [13]. Therefore, the question about the presence of risk factors (or triggers) characteristic for the development of myocardial infarction arises quite reasonably.

One of the analyses of the study examined the relationship between physical activity and risk of MI. It turned out that physical activity in leisure time, as well as work involving light to moderate physical activity (but not heavy physical labour), prevented the development of myocardial infarction. It was found that patients who used a car and TV for a long time had a higher risk of acute myocardial infarction.

Studies have confirmed the role of risk factors in the development of CHD along with AMI. Although CHD risk factors are generally known, the importance of each of them manifests itself in different proportions in different regions and among different populations [17]. It is known that an angina attack lasts for a certain time and can lead to MI [18]. In some patients, it may not cause MI at all. Therefore, it is more correct to speculate about the presence of risk factors (or triggers) specific to the development of AMI. This question can be answered from a database of hospitals specialising in acute care when the disease is detected. It is important to note that not all hospitals can provide this information.

A recent analysis of this study examined the relationship between physical activity and risk factors for MI. The results of this study

showed that work related physical activity with mild to moderate pain (but not heavy physical labour) prevented the development of MI.

The influence of risk factors on the development of myocardial infarction has been proven in many studies worldwide, but the prevalence and combination of known risk factors may vary by geographic region, creating the most important individual risk factors for a particular disease. Clinical guidelines new techniques (particularly magnetic resonance imaging, computed tomography, etc.) may help to better predict risk.

The study of heart rate variability is a special method that allows assessing the state of the cardiovascular system with a high level of informativeness [24]. It is proved that changes in parameters used in myocardial infarction are associated with unfavourable cardiovascular events. Mini - study is used to assess the functional state of the organism, prognosis of diseases, selection of optimal treatment taking into account the vegetative state of the person. In healthy people, the interval between heart beats is constantly changing. Change in heart rate is a universal response of the body to any stimulus. It is determined by the balance between the effects of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system. This is the basis for various methods of analysing MI. It was found that heart rate is an indicator of abnormalities occurring in the autonomic nervous system, and changes in heart rate are an early prognostic sign of cardiovascular pathology [25]. Mini - study is used in clinical practice to prescribe drug doses according to the autonomic state of the organism, as well as to assess the effectiveness of treatment. In patients with postinfarction atherosclerosis, the development of life-threatening arrhythmias is associated with an increased risk of sudden death. Decreased left ventricular fraction or persistent ventricular tachycardia, together with palpitations and symptoms of heart failure, are an important risk sign for poor patient outcomes. The drugs affecting the cardiovascular system used in AMI are beta-blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and angiotensin 2 receptor blockers. The characteristic drugs are beta-adrenoblockers, which not only affect the normalisation of the sympathetic/parasympathetic system ratio, but also reduce heart rate. Thus, the heart rate spectrum changes: the high-frequency component increases, and the influence of the mid-frequency and low-frequency components decreases. [22]

Genetic methods have also been prescribed to identify patients at high risk of developing MI, and experimental stem cell therapies have also been performed [26]. However, to date, these methods have been of little use to the clinician. Several attempts have been made to create universal estimates to calculate the risk of serious cardiovascular disease, including AMI.

For a long time, data from individual observational studies conducted on randomised patient elections have been studied to examine the prevalence, course and outcomes of diseases [9]. These data cannot reflect the actual morbidity in the cities where these clinics are located, even if they are provided by qualified medical staff.

The emergence of epidemiology as a science made it possible to formulate the basic principles of conducting a number of studies to obtain real information about the prevalence of diseases, the characteristics and course of their occurrence, outcomes, etc. One of the first major epidemiological studies in the field of cardiology revealed the main factors contributing to the development of cardiovascular diseases, as well as the role of these diseases in mortality [19].

But epidemiological studies are not the best way to study a particular disease, especially since we have to study its course, outcomes, and the effectiveness of treatment methods. Obviously, the less prevalent a particular disease is, the more difficult it will be to use epidemiological studies to solve the above problems. In the middle of the 20th century, the most accurate way to obtain information on the actual clinical course of a disease, its outcomes, etc. in certain regions

in certain medical institutions is to use hospital statistics. The clinical studies performed may be of value in studying the course of the disease and its outcome. The increasing number of patients with comorbidities in recent years has complicated ongoing clinical trials. Therefore, the results of these studies can be summarised by recognising that controlled clinical trials are ideal models for studying the effects of specific treatments on disease outcomes [19]. In addition, it should not be forgotten that controlled clinical trials almost always have one specific aim, usually to study the effect of a particular drug (or treatment).

In the population under sixty-five years of age, the mortality of a patient with AMI before hospitalisation is one in fifty. For patients older than this age, the risk increases to one in ten patients. Among patients over sixty-five years of age, the risk of death is high between 30 days and 1 year of disease. The mortality rate in middle-aged patients is 15%, and in elderly patients the rate is 25%. In half of patients over 65 years old myocardial infarction is caused by acute complications of the disease in the acute period [9, 10].

To date, there are requirements for determining the frequency of occurrence of age-related risk factors. The increased incidence is dominated by a combination of three or more risk factors, among which arterial hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus are of particular importance. Obesity, obesity and excessive alcohol consumption are frequent risk factors in elderly patients. Causes of coronary heart disease in the elderly are often acute respiratory viral infections, exacerbation of chronic somatic diseases, discontinuation of medications that need to be taken continuously. Elderly patients more often go to hospital late due to worsening clinical condition, which aggravates clinical outcomes [5, 20].

Myocardial infarction in elderly patients often has an atypical presentation. Patients often complain of chest pain, choking, rapid or slow heartbeat, as well as neurological complaints. The occurrence of such a variety of clinical complaints is influenced by a decrease in the sensitivity of the receptor apparatus of the heart to pain sensitivity against the background of atherosclerosis, a decrease in the general reactivity of the body of the elderly, comorbid diseases. Prolonged course of the disease and development of severe clinical symptoms are associated with redistribution of blood flow around the artery with thrombosis of collateral vessels. Myocardial infarction in elderly patients is often accompanied by decompensated heart failure, cardiogenic shock, thrombosis of arteries of other organs and systems, rhythm and conduction disorders. It should be noted that the incidence of early coronary complications increases with age. Atrial fibrillation on the background of myocardial infarction occurs five times more often in older patients. The incidence of AV blockade in middle-aged patients is three times higher than in middle-aged patients [21].

Several studies in elderly patients with persistent ST-segment elevation above the insula have shown that patients have better clinical outcomes. A comparative study of patients of appropriate age receiving regular conservative treatment showed that the rate of recurrent infarction and disability was partially reduced in patients who underwent surgery for MI [14]. This creates certain difficulties in the selection of drugs for comorbid diseases in elderly patients on conservative treatment.

The current recommendations are not age appropriate. We believe that the approach to treatment of the patients studied above should be individualised considering age. Urgent thrombolytic therapy or stenting of coronary arteries in patients with high and extremely high risk of early death, ACS procedures and single regimen development remains one of the urgent tasks of our time. Obesity and diabetes leading to cardiovascular diseases are becoming one of the urgent problems of our time.

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